

Advancement in Latest Plant Hormone: The Brassinosteroids

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Brassinosteroids (the new sixth class of plant growth hormone) are a group of steroids hormones, essentially important for plant development and growth. Essentially these brassinosteroids participate in the regulation of numerous developmental processes, including root and shoot growth, vascular differentiation, fertility, flowering, and seed germination, as well as in responding to environmental stresses. These compounds were first discovered in rapeseed plant pollen. The most known brassinosteroids is brassinolide. There are about 70 types of BRs have been found in algae, ferns, gymnosperms, and angiosperms, but not bacteria.

Types of brassinosteroids

Approximately 70 naturally occurring polyhydroxy steroids known as Brassinosteroids.

These are of mainly of two types

A) Brassinolide

B) Castasterone.

Brassinolide was the first brassinosteroid which was isolated in 1979, when pollen grain from *Brassica napus* was shown to promote stem elongation and cell divisions, and the biologically active molecule was isolated. The yield of brassinosteroid from 230 kg of *Brassica napus* was only 10 mg.

Parts of Plants Where Brassinosteroids are Usually Found

Brassinosteroids have been found in various species of plants, including monoplast freshwater algae and brown algae, indicating that BRs differ among distinct tissue of individual species, pollen, immature seeds, roots and flowers were found to have the highest content, ranging from 1-100 ng/g (fresh weight), white shoots and leaves have lower amounts 0.01-0.1 ng/g fresh weight. The content and distributions of different BR analogues also vary among tissues. Unlike other hormones endogenous BRs do not move between tissues but function in a paracrine or autocrine way as demonstrated by grafting experiment using a BR deficient of mutant pea. One reason for this is likely that BR biosynthesis genes are widespread in various tissues of plant and BRs can be synthesized in situ. Long distance effects of BRs depend on their crosstalk with other hormones like auxins and gibberellins. However, BRs need transporting from their synthesis sites in ER to the plasma membrane and early endosomal compartments where they are perceived through passive or active intracellular transport.

Structure of Brassinosteroid

Brassinosteroids are classified as C₁₇, C₂₈ or C₂₉ based on different alkyl-substitution patterns of the side chains. In general, a transfused A/B ring system with two hydroxyl groups at ring A and 6-ketone or 7-oxa-6-ketone system at ring B are required for active BRs. The chemical structure of brassinolide (22R,23R,24S) -2a,3a,22,23-tetrahydroxy-24-methyl-B-homo-7-oxa-cholestan-6-one). Other BRs differ from BL within boxed area (a) and (b) on the basis of

a 5 alpha-cholestane skeleton. Additionally, BR conjugated forms with sugars or fatty acids have also been found, which are the inactive products of BR metabolism.

Fig. The chemical structure of brassinolide (BL) with the steroid rings labeled as A,B,C, and D. The parts within the dash lines can be substituted by different groups, as described in text.

Hormonal activity of BRs

1. Works with auxin- cell expansion and elongation.
2. BRs signal transduction has been studied during vascular differentiation.
3. Active role in pollen tube formation.
4. Delaying senescence is one of the major hormonal activities.
5. Brassinosteroids help plants to be protected against chilling and drought.
6. BRs help to counteract stress.
7. Promotion of apical dominance.
8. Increases resistance to Freezing.
9. Inhibition of root growth
10. Enhancement in seed germination.
11. Increased production of ethylene.
12. Prevention of premature abscission of the fruit .

Applications of BRs

1. Application of BRs to cucumber increases metabolism and removes the residual effects of pesticides.
2. 28-homo BL is most effective in increasing tolerance to high temperature.
3. Effective in growth of Paddy when applied
4. 24- epiBL have protective role on shoot, root length also on soluble protein, proline content, and peroxidase.
5. Helps to overcome unfavourable cultural and environmental conditions.
6. Application of BRs is found to be favourable for horticultural crops.
7. Help to bridge the gap between consumers health concerns and the producers need for growth.
8. Does not contribute to co-evolution of pests.
9. Also used in tissue cultures, for cell enlargement.
10. It was reported that BRs at low concentration acted as inhibitor of growth of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*.

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